

LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING ADVERBIAL MODIFIER OF PLACE IN CHINESE

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Abstract: *This article presents the main features of the adverbial modifier of place, its positions in the sentence, lexical units expressing the adverbial modifier of the place, as well as the points of view of foreign and Chinese scientists on this issue. The article also presents new aspects of the problem of the issue under consideration, which are revealed in the course of the study. These aspects of the problem can become a new focus for the further research.*

Keywords and expressions: *Chinese grammar, adverbial modifier of place, preposition, pronoun, lexical units, position, scientific statement.*

INTRODUCTION

The grammar of the Chinese has its own characteristics in the use of various parts of speech and sentence parts. In current article, we consider the features of the use of various lexical units involved in the formation of the adverbial modifier of place in a sentence, as well as the opinions of famous sinologists in considering this issue.

Well known, that in the syntax, adverbial modifier (状语) is a secondary part of the sentence, which usually expressed by adverb or prepositional case form of noun and indicates time, place, reason, target, scope, aspect and some other accompanying characteristics of the communication. [Ojegov S.I., Schwedova N.Y.: 674]

Adverbial modifier of place, which answers to “where?” question, expresses the place of the action, direction and the way of movement. Adverbial modifier of place is expressed by the adverbs of place, nouns in form of prepositional case with or without preposition and the phrasal combinations.

The aim of our research is an exposure of some features of the adverbial modifier of place in Chinese, its functions and the way of use lexical units and link-words in the sentence, which are necessary for expression of the adverbial modifier of the place.

In order to clarify the degree of study of this issue, we turned to some scientific works of the famous sinologists, like Y.V. Rojdestvensky, T.P. Zadoyenko, V.M. Solnsev, S.E. Yaxontov, 刘月华, 潘文娱, where considered the main issues, related with adverbial modifier of place, in particular with its significance, positions in the sentence and also the ways of its expression. In Chinese, the adverbial modifier divides into two classes: statistic and dynamic. Statistic- adverbial modifier, which answers to the question “where?” [Zadoyenko: 56].

In Chinese language, there are different modes of expression:

A. By the title of place (expressed as a noun)

北京 - Běijīng - Beijing

官洲 Guān zhōu - Guanzhou

香港 - Xiānggǎng - Hong Kong

上海 - Shànghǎi - Shanghai

B. By the adverb of place

这里 - zhèlǐ - here

那里 - nàlǐ - there

这边 - zhèbiān - here

那边 - nàbiān - there

这儿 - zhèr - here 那儿 - nàr - there

C. By the adverb of place and pronoun

你那儿 – Nǐ nàr – there you

你这儿 – Nǐ zhèr – here you

在你们那儿有没有图书馆？ - zài nǐmen nàr yǒu mei yǒu túshūguǎn?

Do you have there a library?

D. By special use, which verifies place of the object's situation in the space and it takes up the following scheme: 在 (zài) + noun + postposition, which verifies the place of situation.

Postpositions: [Li Dejin: 214]

外 wài – outside

左 zuǒ – left

内 nèi – inside

右 yòu – right

下 xià – under

前 qián – in front

上 shàng – above

后 hòu – behind¹

They can be used separately or with suffix 边 biān and 面 miàn. The following words cannot be used separately:

对面 – duìmiàn – opposite

旁边 – pángbian – beside

中间 – zhōngjian – in the middle

So, we will give several examples due to the above-mentioned scheme:

在桌子下面 – zài zhuōzǐ xiàmiàn - под столом

在桌子上面 – zài zhuōzǐ shàngmiàn - на столе

Postpositions usually not used after the geographic titles and places, and after the words, which denote the cardinal points:

北 – běi – the North

南 – nán – the South

西 – xī – the West

东 – dōng – the East

Position of the static adverbial adjunct of place in the sentence.

Position of the static adverbial adjunct of place in the sentence depends on that position, what the predicate is expressed by.

A. According to A.A. Karimov's opinion, depending on the way of expression, “在” link-word can take different positions in the sentences. [Karimov: 67]

If “在” preposition is expressed by the verb, then it takes position before adverbial modifier of place.

For example:

她在教室 – She is in the classroom.

If “在” comes as a preposition, then it takes position before adverbial modifier of place, but the sentence should also have verb.

¹ Antonymic words, like 上 shàng/下 xià, 前 qián/后 hòu simultaneously can be used to express the time and place of an action.

If the adverbial modifier of place is expressed by pronoun or noun, which denotes human, then after this kind of adverbial modifier we usually use adverb of place or noun with the meaning of place.

It is wrong to say:

他们的飞机票在王刚 tāmen de fēijī piào zài Wáng gang-

The following sentence is correct:

他们的飞机票在王刚那儿 tāmen de fēijī piào zài Wáng gāng nàr-

Our ticket for the Bei jing opera is in Van Gang`s house.

If the adverbial modifier of place is already expressed by noun, which denotes a place or geographical title, then the foregoing rule is not used here:

我在北京 – tā zài Běijīng – He is in Beijing

B. If predicate expressed by the verb 有 (yǒu), then we must use the adverbial modifier before it (before 有 (yǒu)). For example:

桌子上有报纸 -zhuōzǐ shàng yǒu bàozhǐ – There are newspapers on the table.

你们这儿有多少学生? -nǐmen zhèr yǒu duōshǎo xuéshēng? - How many students do you have here?

A. If predicate is expressed by verb with the meaning of availability (existence) 是 (shì), then the adverbial modifier must be used before it (before 是 (shì)):

小吃店对面是我的家- xiǎochīdiàn duìmiàn shì wǒ de jiā- There is my house in front of the snack-bar.

Negative form:

小吃店对面不是我的家-xiǎochīdiàn duìmiàn bú shì wǒ de jiā- There is not my house in front of the snack-bar.

The difference between “有” sentence and “是” sentence is the following:

In the sentence with “有” interlocutor is informed about a thing, that he don`t know.

In the sentence with “是” you confirm the information, which the interlocutor talks about or refute it.

In the presence of usual verbal predicate, the adverbial adjunct of place can be used between subject and predicate or after the predicate.

Chiefly, we should remember the following rule: If there is a preposition 在 (zài) in the sentence, then the adverbial adjunct of place must be used after it (after preposition 在 (zài)).

There is a group of verbs of state (condition):

放 – Fàng – to put

住 – Zhù – to live

躺 – Tǎng – to lie

坐 – Zuò – to sit

站 – Zhàn – to stand

挂 – Guà – to hang. Dynamic adverbial modifier of place is an adverbial modifier of place, which answers to the question: “where?”, “where...from?”.

Position of the dynamic adverbial modifier of place in the sentence:

A. Dynamic adverbial modifier can be used after the verb-predicate if the verb-predicate denotes the action to the speaker or from the speaker and it is constructed with the aid of the words 来 (lái) and 去 (qù). For example:

明天晚他上来我家里-ming tian wǎnshang tā lái wǒ jiā li.- Tomorrow in the evening, he will come to my home.

我夏天想去北京学习-wǒ xiàtiān xiǎng qù Běijīng xuéxí- In summer I am going to China to study.

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